

Equations of Motion for the Cart-pole

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Abstract

The cart-pole is a well-known nonlinear dynamical system frequently used as benchmark in control theory. It has been studied in depth in both simulation and real mechanisms, and its control has probably been solved by using each known method. Lately, it has also been used as a benchmark for the most complex and powerful deep reinforcement learning-based control methods. However, since its dynamical model is already available in many software repositories, its theoretical study is neglected. This report shows how to apply conventional methods to derive the equations of motion for the cart-pole. It is also intended to serve as an example for the study of other mechanisms, such as the acrobot or the multiple pendulum.

Keywords: Dynamical systems; Nonlinear dynamics; Lagrangian mechanics; Equations of motion; Cart-pole system.

1 Introduction

The cart-pole is a nonlinear dynamical system consisting of a simple pendulum or pole mounted on a platform or cart. It has been frequently studied because it is a simplified model of many real robotic mechanisms and devices [1]. It is also used as a reference in control theory to compare the results when different approaches and to check if a particular artificial intelligence technique is capable of solving such control problems [2–5]. Lately, it has also been used as a benchmark for the most powerful deep reinforcement learning-based control methods [6, 7]. Its model is available in several software repositories [8] and it is frequently used without a minimal theoretical study to understand its complexity.

The object of this report is to study the dynamics of such a system and to derive the equations that describe the motion. The study is also intended to serve as an example for analyzing similar mechanisms.

This report is organized as follows. First, we describe the dynamical system by introducing its elements and the control problems that are usually considered. Next, we define the variables that describe the state of the cart-pole system and the forces that act over the system to obtain the equations of motion by applying basic concepts of Lagrangian mechanics. Then, we briefly outline how to determine situations in which the system has a linear behavior in order to use the most appropriate control techniques. Finally, we summarize the method in order to indicate how it could be applied to similar problems.

2 System Description

The cart-pole consists of a pendulum or pole mounted on a platform or cart as shown in Fig. 1. The platform can move on a track in one direction, back and forth. This motion is primarily

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due to the application of an external force, which is the only way to act on the system. The pendulum is attached to the platform by an underactuated joint that allows the pendulum to swing freely. It is the movement of the cart that causes the pendulum to swing. In turn, these oscillations are transmitted to the cart, which affects the stability of the whole system. It is usual to consider external disturbances, measurement noise, and frictions that modify the dynamics of the system.

Figure 1: Schematic of the cart-pole system, where M is the mass of the cart, x is its coordinate on the horizontal axis, f_x is the magnitude of the force on the horizontal axis, m is the mass of the pendulum, L is the length of its arm, θ is the angle of the pendulum measured counterclockwise ($\theta = 0$ when it is down), and (x_p, y_p) is the end of the pole in the world coordinate frame.

Generally, two control problems are considered. Starting from a position of rest, with the pendulum downward, we try to reach a position with the pendulum above the cart. It is called the swing-up problem. The balancing problem is more common because of its linear behavior around the equilibrium point. Here, the goal is to keep the pendulum in equilibrium vertically above the cart. The movement of the pendulum is always achieved by the force applied to the cart. Usually, the area in which the cart can move is also restricted.

3 Equations of Motion

The state \vec{x} of the system is determined by four variables: x , the position of the cart, \dot{x} , its linear velocity, θ , the angle of the pendulum, and $\dot{\theta}$, its angular velocity.

The position of the pendulum's end (x_p, y_p) in the world coordinate frame is

$$x_p = x + L \sin \theta \quad (1)$$

$$y_p = -L \cos \theta \quad (2)$$

where L is the length of the pendulum.

The velocity components of the pendulum's end (\dot{x}_p, \dot{y}_p) are obtained by deriving (1) and (2) as a function of t .¹

$$\dot{x}_p = \frac{d}{dt}x_p = \dot{x} + L\dot{\theta} \cos \theta \quad (3)$$

$$\dot{y}_p = \frac{d}{dt}y_p = L\dot{\theta} \sin \theta \quad (4)$$

We are going to obtain the dynamics of this nonlinear system applying the formulation of the Lagrangian mechanics since it simplifies considerably the approach and the resolution of the problem in comparison with the formulation of the classical mechanics. The Lagrangian \mathcal{L} is defined from the kinetic energy T and the potential energy U of the system as

$$\mathcal{L} = T - U \quad (5)$$

¹Note that in this case, L is constant, but x , y and θ depend on t . This must be taken into account when deriving. For example, $\frac{d}{dt} \sin \theta = \dot{\theta} \cos \theta$.

The kinetic energy T of the system is calculated as the sum of the kinetic energies of all the elements (or particles) involved, in this case, the platform and the pendulum. Taking into account the expressions of the pendulum velocity (3) and (4), and operating, the kinetic energy T is

$$\begin{aligned} T &= \frac{1}{2}M\dot{x}^2 + \frac{1}{2}m(\dot{x}_p^2 + \dot{y}_p^2) \\ &= \frac{1}{2}M\dot{x}^2 + \frac{1}{2}m\left((\dot{x} + L\dot{\theta}\cos\theta)^2 + (L\dot{\theta}\sin\theta)^2\right) \\ &= \frac{1}{2}(M+m)\dot{x}^2 + m\dot{x}L\dot{\theta}\cos\theta + \frac{1}{2}mL^2\dot{\theta}^2 \end{aligned} \quad (6)$$

where M denotes the mass of the cart and m denotes the mass of the pendulum.

The potential energy U of the system is obtained by considering the elements that vary their position in the vertical axis, which is affected by the acceleration of gravity, denoted by g , and is defined as

$$U = mgy_p = -mgL\cos\theta \quad (7)$$

Substituting the values of the energies (6) and (7) into (5), the Lagrangian \mathcal{L} becomes

$$\mathcal{L} = \frac{1}{2}(M+m)\dot{x}^2 + m\dot{x}L\dot{\theta}\cos\theta + \frac{1}{2}mL^2\dot{\theta}^2 + mgL\cos\theta \quad (8)$$

To solve it, we apply the Euler-Lagrange equation on each coordinate of the Lagrangian. The equation for the x coordinate is

$$\frac{d}{dt}\frac{\partial\mathcal{L}}{\partial\dot{x}} - \frac{\partial\mathcal{L}}{\partial x} = F_x \quad (9)$$

where F_x represent the non conservative external generalized forces, in this case, the control force f_x applied to the cart and the attenuation due to the damping $-\delta\dot{x}$, where δ is the coefficient of friction between cart and track. Calculating the results of each of the derivatives separately

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial\mathcal{L}}{\partial x} &= 0 \\ \frac{\partial\mathcal{L}}{\partial\dot{x}} &= (M+m)\dot{x} + mL\dot{\theta}\cos\theta \\ \frac{d}{dt}\frac{\partial\mathcal{L}}{\partial\dot{x}} &= (M+m)\ddot{x} + mL\ddot{\theta}\cos\theta - mL\dot{\theta}^2\sin\theta \end{aligned}$$

and introducing them in (9), we get the first equation describing the dynamics of the system

$$(M+m)\ddot{x} + mL\ddot{\theta}\cos\theta - mL\dot{\theta}^2\sin\theta = f_x - \delta\dot{x} \quad (10)$$

where f_x is the magnitude of the force applied to the cart and δ is the coefficient of friction.

The Euler-Lagrange equation for the system second coordinate θ is

$$\frac{d}{dt}\frac{\partial\mathcal{L}}{\partial\dot{\theta}} - \frac{\partial\mathcal{L}}{\partial\theta} = 0 \quad (11)$$

Following the same procedure as before, we calculate the results of each of the derivatives separately

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial\mathcal{L}}{\partial\theta} &= -m\dot{x}L\dot{\theta}\sin\theta - mgL\sin\theta \\ \frac{\partial\mathcal{L}}{\partial\dot{\theta}} &= m\dot{x}L\cos\theta + mL^2\dot{\theta} \\ \frac{d}{dt}\frac{\partial\mathcal{L}}{\partial\dot{\theta}} &= m\ddot{x}L\cos\theta - \dot{\theta}m\dot{x}L\sin\theta + mL^2\ddot{\theta} \end{aligned}$$

and introducing them into (11), thus obtaining the second equation describing the dynamics of the system

$$m\ddot{x}L \cos \theta + mL^2\ddot{\theta} + mgL \sin \theta = 0 \quad (12)$$

From (10) and (12), we derive \ddot{x} and $\ddot{\theta}$, which describe the dynamic behavior of the entire cart-pole system.

$$\ddot{x} = \frac{f_x - \delta\dot{x} + m \sin \theta (g \cos \theta + L\dot{\theta}^2)}{M + m \sin^2 \theta} \quad (13)$$

$$\ddot{\theta} = \frac{-f_x \cos \theta - (mL\dot{\theta}^2 \sin \theta - \delta\dot{x}) \cos \theta - (M + m)g \sin \theta}{L(M + m \sin^2 \theta)} \quad (14)$$

4 Linearization

Like many others, the cart-pole dynamical system $\dot{\vec{x}} = f(\vec{x})$, or in the general form $\dot{\vec{x}} = f(\vec{x}, \vec{u}, t)$ to consider control inputs and time, is nonlinear. In such cases, the system is usually linearized at equilibrium points \vec{x}_e that are those where $f(\vec{x}_e, \vec{u}_e) = 0$. This allows for the application of simpler linear control techniques than the nonlinear methods.

The linearization procedure is performed by calculating the partial derivatives of $f(\vec{x})$ with respect to each of the state variables and the control inputs expressed by a Jacobian matrix [9]. In this case the Jacobian matrices are

$$A = \left. \frac{\partial f(\vec{x})}{\partial \vec{x}} \right|_{\vec{x}_e, \vec{u}_e} = \begin{bmatrix} \partial f_1/\partial x_1 & \partial f_1/\partial x_2 & \partial f_1/\partial x_3 & \partial f_1/\partial x_4 \\ \partial f_2/\partial x_1 & \partial f_2/\partial x_2 & \partial f_2/\partial x_3 & \partial f_2/\partial x_4 \\ \partial f_3/\partial x_1 & \partial f_3/\partial x_2 & \partial f_3/\partial x_3 & \partial f_3/\partial x_4 \\ \partial f_4/\partial x_1 & \partial f_4/\partial x_2 & \partial f_4/\partial x_3 & \partial f_4/\partial x_4 \end{bmatrix} \quad B = \left. \frac{\partial f(\vec{x})}{\partial \vec{u}} \right|_{\vec{x}_e, \vec{u}_e} = \begin{bmatrix} \partial f_1/\partial u \\ \partial f_2/\partial u \\ \partial f_3/\partial u \\ \partial f_4/\partial u \end{bmatrix}$$

where $f_1(\vec{x}) = \dot{x}$, $f_2(\vec{x}) = \dot{x}$, given in (13), $f_3(\vec{x}) = \dot{\theta}$ and $f_4(\vec{x}) = \dot{\theta}$, given in (14), $\vec{x} = [x \ \dot{x} \ \theta \ \dot{\theta}]^T$ is the state vector and \vec{u} is the control input vector, for the cart-pole $u = f_x$.

After linearization, the nonlinear system $\dot{\vec{x}} = f(\vec{x})$ is usually written as $\dot{\vec{x}} = A\vec{x} + B\vec{u}$.

The cart-pole system has two equilibrium points corresponding to the positions of the pendulum down ($\theta = 0$) and up ($\theta = \pi$), and when it is stationary ($\dot{x} = 0$, $\dot{\theta} = 0$). The variable x that describes the position along the axis is free, i.e., it does not matter where the cart-pole is.

The matrices A and B are similar for both points except for the sign of some of the elements. Thus, we introduce $b = -1$ for the position down and $b = +1$ for up. Note that the first point is stable and the second one is unstable.

$$A = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & -\delta/M & -b g m/M & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \\ 0 & -b \delta/(ML) & b g(M+m)/(ML) & 0 \end{bmatrix} \quad B = \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ 1/M \\ 0 \\ b/(ML) \end{bmatrix} \quad (15)$$

5 Concluding remarks

The report describes how to derive the equations of motion for the cart-pole system. First, we need to define the pendulum's end in the world coordinate frame. Then, we calculate the velocity components in each axis that are used to obtain the kinetic and potential energies in order to apply the Lagrangian formulation to study the dynamical system. Finally, we introduce external forces and obtain the equations of motion. The procedure for determining the configurations in which the system can show linear behavior is also described.

From here we could keep studying the system behavior analyzing the stability with and without external forces, the controllability and the observability or designing a controller such as an LQR by manipulating the system response through the control law.

References

- [1] Russ Tedrake. *Underactuated Robotics*. Course Notes for MIT 6.832, 2023.
- [2] Andrew G. Barto, Richard S. Sutton, and Charles W. Anderson. Neuronlike adaptive elements that can solve difficult learning control problems. *IEEE Transactions on Systems, Man, and Cybernetics*, SMC-13(5):834–846, 1983.
- [3] G. Cansever and O.F. Ozguven. Application of fuzzy set theory to stabilization of an inverted pendulum by high speed fuzzy logic controller. In *Proc. of MELECON '94. Mediterranean Electrotechnical Conference*, volume 3, pages 1085–1088, 1994.
- [4] Faustino Gomez and Risto Miikkulainen. Incremental evolution of complex general behavior. *Adaptive Behavior*, 5:317–342, 1997.
- [5] Savinay Nagendra, Nikhil Podila, Rashmi Ugarakhod, and Koshy George. Comparison of reinforcement learning algorithms applied to the cart-pole problem. In *Int. Conf. on Advances in Computing, Communications and Informatics (ICACCI)*, pages 26–32, 2017.
- [6] Adam Paszke and Mark Towers. Reinforcement Learning (DQN) Tutorial. PyTorch Documentation, Mar 2017.
- [7] Swagat Kumar. Balancing a cartpole system with reinforcement learning – A tutorial. arXiv:2006.04938, Jun 2020.
- [8] Mark Towers et al. Gymnasium: A standard interface for reinforcement learning environments. arXiv:2407.17032, Nov 2024.
- [9] Steven L. Brunton and J. Nathan Kutz. *Data-Driven Science and Engineering*. Cambridge University Press, Cambridge, MA, 2nd edition, 2022.